

The BiodivERsA database:

a mapping of research on biodiversity and
ecosystem services in Europe over 2005-2015

APPENDIX

APPENDIX I - KEYWORD PROFILE USED TO SEARCH FOR BIODIVERSITY PROJECTS

Note that this profile was applied to the biodiversity projects' lists provided by the BiodivERsA funding partners. This automatic search was completed by a manual screening to exclude non-biodiversity projects for some agencies. In addition, a sample of 100-200 projects was screened to verify that the selected projects were indeed (at least partly) focused on biodiversity.

TERMS				
vegetation	colony or colonies	functional type*	metacommunit*	vulnerability
adaptation	communities	fung*	metagenomic	weed diversity
aedes	community	genera	metapopulation*	weed*
agro-ecological	connectivity	genes	microalga*	wetland*
agroecology	conservation	genetic	microb*	whale*
agro-ecology	conserving	genetic divers*	microbial	wildlife
agrosystem*	coral*	genetic diversity	microbial diversity	woodland*
alga*	crab*	genetic resource*	microorganism*	yam*
alga* diversity	crb	genetic structure	micro-organism*	zoo*
alien species	crustacean*	genetic variation	migrat*	zooplankton*
amphibian diversity	cryptogam*	genom*	moth*	nature improvement area*
amphibian*	cultiva*	genotype*	mussel*	nature reserve*
animal diversity	cyanobacteria*	genus	mutant*	nematod* diversity
aphid*	cyanobacteria* diversity	germplasm	mutualis*	nematode*
arable plant*	dairy cow*	grape*	myco* diversity	non-native
arable rotation*	dairy herd*	grass*	native species	observatories or observatory
bacteria*	deer*	grassland*	natura 2000	observing system*
bacteria* diversity	demograph*	grazing behaviour	natural capital	ocean biology
bacteriol*	diatom*	green grey infrastructure*	natural environment*	offspring*
badger*	dipter*	green infrastructure*	natural habitat*	orchid*
banana*	disease*	green roof*	natural heritage	organisms
bat	domestication	habitat adaptation	sea angling	parakeet*
bats	ecological	habitat conservation	sea cucumber*	parasit*
bee	ecological genetics	habitat diversity	seabird*	parasitism
bees	ecological genom*	habitat*	seagrass*	park*
beetle*	ecological invader*	halophyte*	seaweed	pasture*
benth*	ecological network*	hedgerow*	seed*	peatland*
benthos	ecological network*	herbarium	selection	pelagic
biocenosis	ecological speciation	honeybee*	sentinel species	permanent plots
biodivers*	ecology	host*	shellfish species	pest*
bioecological	economics spectrum	hunting	snapper*	phenotyp*
biofilm*	ecosystem diversity	husbandry	specialisation	phylogen*
biogeograph*	ecosystem*	ideotype*	specialization	phylogeograph*
bioindicator*	ecotype*	illegal trade	speciation	phytoplankton*
biological adaption	eel*	insect diversity	specie*	plankton*
biological conservation	egg*	insect*	species composition	plant diversity
biological diversity	elephant*	interspecific	species conservation	plant*
biological indicator*	environmental impact*	intraspecific	species diversity	pollination

biological invasion*	environmental observator*	invasive	species range	pollinator*
biological monitoring	environmental status	invasive plant*	species richness	population dynamics
biological productivity	evoluti*	invasive species	spider* diversity	population*
biome*	evolution*	invertebrate diversity	squid*	predat*
bioremediation	fallow*	invertebrate*	survival	preserv*
biosphere	fauna	ipbes	symbio*	protected
biota	feeding pattern*	jellyfish*	systematics	protected area*
biotic	feeding strateg*	landrace*	taxa	protecti*
bird diversity	field margin*	landscape diversity	taxon*	range change*
bird population*	fish*	larva*	taxonom*	raptor*
bird*	flora	lichen*	tortoise*	recruitment
bivalve*	floristic	life	traits	reef*
boar*	food web	life history trait*	tree species	refugia
breed*	foodweb	livestock*	tree*	reintroduction
bryophyte*	food-web	lotic	trophic	remediat*
bumblebee*	foraminifer*	macrobrachium	tropical *system*	reproducti*
bushmeat	forest*	macroecolog*	turtle*	reptile diversity
bycatch*	fragment* habitat*	mammal diversity	urchin*	reptile*
calophyllum	fragmentation	mammal*	variet*	reserve*
canopy	frog diversity	mangrove*	vegetable*	restoration
cbd	functional diversity	marine monitoring	vegetation type*	restoration
cetacean*	functional ecology	marine survey*	vertebrate*	revegetation
chemical communication	functional group*	marine vertebrate*	virus diversity	rodent*
coexist*	functional redundancy	maternal	virus*	ruminant*
co-exist*	functional trait*	meadow*	vole*	salmon

COMBINATION OF TERMS

benthic	✘	*divers*
coexistence	✘	species
conserv*	✘	ecolog*
conserv*	✘	habitat*
disease*	✘	host*
ecosystem	✘	*divers*
ecosystem*	✘	diversity
ecosystem*	✘	genom*
ecosystem*	✘	organism*
evolution	✘	*divers*
evolution*	✘	species
genetic*	✘	ecology
genetic*	✘	population*
genom*	✘	species
habitat	✘	*divers*
habitat*	✘	species
invasi*	✘	population*
invasi*	✘	species
invasive	✘	insect*
marine	✘	biolog*
ocean	✘	biolog*

APPENDIX II – LIST OF EU OUTERMOST REGIONS (ORS) AND OVERSEAS COUNTRIES AND TERRITORIES (OCTS)

OUTERMOST REGIONS (9)

France

- » French Guiana
- » Martinique
- » Guadeloupe
- » St Martin
- » Mayotte
- » Réunion

Portugal

- » Azores
- » Madeira

Spain

- » Canary Islands

OVERSEAS COUNTRIES & TERRITORIES (25)

United Kingdom

- » Anguilla
- » Bermuda
- » British Antarctic Territory
- » British Indian Ocean Territory
- » British Virgin Islands
- » Cayman Islands
- » Falkland Islands
- » Helena, Ascension Island, Tristan da Cunha
- » Montserrat
- » Pitcairn Island
- » South Georgia and South Sandwich Islands
- » Turks and Caicos Islands

France

- » French Polynesia
- » French Southern and Antarctic Territories
- » New Caledonia and Dependencies
- » Saint Barthelemy
- » St. Pierre and Miquelon
- » Wallis and Futuna Islands

Denmark

- » Greenland

Netherlands

- » Aruba
- » Bonaire
- » Curaçao
- » Saba
- » Sint-Eustatius
- » Sint-Maarten

APPENDIX III - TEMPORAL TRENDS OF BIODIVERSITY RESEARCH FUNDING FOR EACH NATIONAL AGENCY AND THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION OVER THE 2005-2015 PERIOD

APPENDIX IV - CORRELATION BETWEEN BIODIVERSITY FUNDING AND ANNUAL GDP PER COUNTRY.

Based on the annual allocation to biodiversity research projects for each country (data from the national agencies agencies) and the annual GDP of this country. One point corresponds to one year.

